

Empowerment of non-academic employees in a private institution: Basis for leadership enhancement program

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Abstract

This study sought to craft a leadership enhancement program for non-academic personnel of a selected academic institution. The study made use of a descriptive research method that employed a sixty (60)-item self-made questionnaire for data gathering. The study utilized sixty-eight (68) non-academic employees from St. Dominic College of Asia, who were selected based on purposive sampling approach. The findings disclosed that most participants have taken the Bachelor's Degree. The extent of leadership empowerment to them was shown more on stimulating them intellectually due to their tenure. Both their tenure and educational qualifications show that they want to be influenced ideally by their leaders whom they look up to as role model for high ethical behavior, respect, trust, motivation, inspiration, and excellence. The low correlation between the extent of leadership practiced and the participants' attitude towards leadership explained that intellectual stimulation and individual consideration contribute to the low correlation. This study recommends that the leaders should always communicate with employees, listen to their issues, and guide and coach them. Employees should be viewed as individuals with distinct needs and desires to continue the recently offered programs by the institution like the Scholarship / Educational Grant, not only for academic employees but more specifically for non-academic employees or the administrative staffs to help them grow as a person and as a professional.

Keywords: Empowerment. Non-academic employees. Private institution. Leadership enhancement program.

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Introduction

Today, leadership is considered to be a highly valued commodity. Good leaders still intrigue people and individuals become more and more interested in information on how to become effective leaders. In fact, most people have a view that to improve personal, social, and professional lives, one has to exemplify good leadership. Companies now prefer employees with good leadership skills because it is believed that they are assets to an organization (Northouse, 2018).

Empowerment in leadership becomes an important topic in the early 21st century leadership particularly in many companies, whose paradigm has shifted from bureaucratic and authoritarian style of leadership to a more participative style of management, trying to get the employees involved in business processes. Employee empowerment is the practice of providing front-line workers the authority to make decisions that were previously exclusively available to managers (LaMarco, 2018). It is believed that the ability to inspire their staff to achieve maximum achievement distinguishes good leaders. It is critical to consider what empowerment entails and how to best apply it in order for an organization's strength to be realized.

Empowerment is a strategy for including the team in decision-making, giving them a participation role that capitalizes on their own expertise and judgment while also increasing their sense of personal value and devotion to the business. Empowerment also displays that one is a good listener and values the opinions of all members of one's team. When a leader empowers his or her team, he or she inspires people to "row together," increasing the mission's overall success. Empowering people increases their confidence in their ability to carry out a leader's common mission and goals, fosters critical trust in an organization, and creates the secondary level of leadership required when a leader is unavailable to make vital decisions (Huntoon, n.d.).

Various factors such as, but not limited to, leadership structure, management style, and organizational climate, have a psychological effect on employees. It cannot be denied that the management style and structure in an institution are effective on the commitment to work and level of satisfaction of employees. For example, an authoritative and rigid form of government may elicit pressure on the employees as well as on the subordinates' beliefs, expectations, and hopes, while a participatory and flexible form of administration may result to the creation of more opportunities for exposure to potentials, commitment to work, and improvement of psychological state. Because organizations come up with events for their own success, employees are forced to adjust their own behaviors for the goals of the organization. Employees are susceptible to getting attached to their jobs, which affects their psychological state. It is apparent that a worker joins a company bringing his/her personal needs and goals, indirectly making a mutual psychological deal with his/her company to achieve the said goals and to be able to provide for his/her needs.

Thus, the ability of the organization to meet the said needs of the employee results to the improvement of one's satisfaction in his/her work and likewise helps increase the attachment of the employee to the organization. Further, managers play an important role in helping employees adapt to the environment of the organization, and in ensuring that they stay in the company. This is because a manager's style of leadership plays an essential role in an employee's ability to adapt to the organization. An employee, when given a job that is suitable for him/her, provided with adequate responsibilities and authority, and shown support by his/her manager, is ought to be more committed to his/her work (Sahin et al., 2014).

Leadership empowerment is risky, but it brings good results to the organization that practices it, as it promotes profound commitment of subordinates because their voices are heard and respected in the organization. Academic institutions are organizations that experience various transactions and operations to serve their customers quality education. Quality education entails quality service, not only by the academic community but even the non-academic aspect of the organization, the so-called administrative support groups, which are composed of non-academic personnel from the registrar's office, finance department, personnel department, utility and general services department, and even the security department. They form part the skeleton of an academic organization because without them, the academic community could never provide quality services to its clientele—the students.

Hence, the main aim of this study is to craft an evidence-based leadership enhancement program for the non-academic personnel which is grounded on a solid research and empirical study. Further this study determines the extent of the practice of leadership empowerment of the non-academic personnel in a selected academic institution according to their readiness.

This study may benefit the academic institution to assess how empowered their workers by providing an empirical study that may serve as a basis for their decision making which can also address the need of the academic institution towards optimizing leadership empowerment; the non-academic personnel to embrace leadership empowerment in the institution, making them more productive and effective; the researcher to learn the intricacies of empowered leadership for her personal consumption and to be better asset to her organization and for her to develop her leadership skills; and the future researchers to work on leadership empowerment.

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive, correlational research design of quantitative research and the test of difference. Descriptive study concerned with the description of the study variables which include determining the frequency and percentage, mean, and standard deviation; while correlational study talks on establishing the relationship of variables using the rigors of inferential statistics which was used in determining the relationship between the extent of leadership empowerment practiced and the participant's readiness. Test of difference compared the variables to see if they are different from each other.

This study was conducted in St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite. All non-academic employees with the total number of eighty-six (86) were targeted and recruited for this study with the assistance of the Human Resource Office. Moreover, purposive sampling approach was used to focus on the particular characteristics of the population that was best enabled to answer the research questions. Participants were chosen with the following criteria in mind: non-academic employee of St. Dominic College of Asia, should not be the head of a department or office, minimum of one (1) year in service and a degree holder. The total number of respondents participated in this study was sixty-eight (68), which is 79.07% of the total population.

A researcher-made questionnaire was utilized in this study. This questionnaire was validated and piloted by three (3) experts from this institution to determine its reliability using the Cronbach alpha. The examination resulted to Cronbach's value of 0.971, with an interpretation of "excellent". Therefore, the test was very reliable. The questionnaire was composed of two (2) parts: the extent of utilization of leadership empowerment, and the attitude and readiness of respondents towards full implementation of leadership empowerment in the institution.

A letter of request was forwarded to the Human Resource Office of St. Dominic College of Asia to request for the number of non-academic employees and for their permit to allow the researcher to conduct the study and gather data. After the data gathering, the researcher tabulated the results and sought the help of a statistician for data analysis.

Descriptive statistics using frequency, percentage, means, and standard deviations were applied to determine the extent of the leadership empowerment of non-academic employees that is being practiced in the academic institution. A Pearson r is also used to test if there is a significant relationship between the extent of leadership empowerment practiced and the readiness of the participants. Moreover, SPSS version 25 was used for the data management.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Respondents' educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's degree	59	86.76
Master's degree	7	10.29
Associate degree	2	2.94

Table 1 presents the respondents' educational attainment. A vast majority of the respondents, which is 86.76%, completed "Bachelor's degree". It is followed by "Master's degree" and "Associate degree" with a percentage of 10.29% and 2.94%, respectively. This means that most of the participants have just finished their bachelor's degree and landed their first job.

Table 2. Extent of leadership empowerment as to idealized influence

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My superior is a good role model to me as a leader.	4.04	0.92	Agree
2. I want to imitate what my superior has been doing as a leader.	3.63	0.99	Agree
3. My superior is willing to take risks in his/her decision making.	4.15	0.85	Agree
4. My superior is consistent in all his/her decision making, whether it pleases us or not.	3.85	0.90	Agree
5. My superior exemplifies a high level of honesty and integrity in everything he/she does, whether we see it or not.	4.15	0.92	Agree
Overall	3.96	0.78	Agree

Table 2 provides the extent of leadership empowerment as to idealized influence. Participants “agreed” that the concept of “idealized influence” is being practiced in the institution, as evidenced from the obtained overall mean rating of 3.96. “Their superior exemplifies a high level of honesty and integrity in everything he/she does, whether they see it or not” ($x=4.15$, $SD=0.92$) and “their superior is willing to take risks in his/her decision making” ($x=4.15$, $SD=0.85$) contributed the most. This means that participants believed as what they have witnessed that their superiors exemplify a high level of honesty and integrity in everything they do and willing to take risks in their decision making. These are followed by “their superior is a good role model to them as a leader” ($x=4.04$, $S.D.=0.92$) and “their superior is consistent in all his/her decision making, whether it pleases them or not” ($x=3.85$, $S.D.=0.90$). The least practiced is they “want to imitate what their superior has been doing as a leader” ($x=3.63$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained S.D. which is equal to 0.99. Despite of having a high level of honesty and integrity and willingness to take risks, respondents might still witness other factor or negative side on their superiors as a result of being least in imitating what they have been doing as a leader.

An empowered leader must be honest, committed and respectable (Murari, 2015) and consistent in decision making (Hollander, 2009). The leader serves as an example of good ethical behavior, instilling pride, respect, and trust (Bass, 1985). As noted by Lau (2010), when employees perceive that a leader is trustworthy, they seek to improve more their performance. One of the few traits similar to all trust situations is the willingness to take risks (Johnson-George & Swap, 1982).

Table 3. Extent of leadership empowerment as to inspirational motivation

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am truly inspired with every act of my superior.	3.91	1.00	Agree
2. The actions of my superior give meaning to my work as a follower.	4.00	0.88	Agree
3. The actions of my superior keep challenging me to do better in everything I do.	4.09	0.84	Agree
4. My superior engages and involves us in the development of our department’s vision for the future.	4.13	0.93	Agree
5. My superior exemplifies a high level of honesty and integrity in everything he/she does, whether we see it or not.	4.09	0.94	Agree
Overall	4.04	0.81	Agree

Table 3 presents the extent of leadership empowerment as to inspirational motivation. Based on the results of the study, the extent of leadership empowerment as to inspirational motivation that the leaders practiced has an overall mean rating of 4.04. Followers “agreed” that the concept of “inspirational motivation” is being practiced by the leaders. The “superior engages and involves us in the development of our department’s vision for the future” ($x=4.13$, $SD=0.93$) contributed the most. This means respondents believed as what they have experienced that their superiors are giving them inspirational motivation as they are being engaged and involved in the development of their department’s vision for the future. It is followed by the “superior communicates his/her clear expectations to each of us as part of the team” ($x=4.09$, $SD=0.94$) and “actions of my superior keep challenging me to do better in everything I do” ($x=4.09$, $SD=0.84$). The “actions of my superior give meaning to my work as a follower” ($x=4.00$, $SD=0.88$) is second to the last and the least is that they are “truly inspired with every act of their superior” ($x=3.91$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained SD which is equal to 1.00. Despite of engaging and involving them in organizational development, participants are still relatively inspired with every act of their leaders as a result of being the least. This could be mean that respondents have seen other factors that can contribute for them to be truly inspired by their superiors.

Leaders with inspirational motivation challenge followers (Bass, 1985) and motivate employees to go above and beyond the call of duty and complete tasks in a flexible manner (Pearson & Moomaw, 2005), have high expectations and support the experience of his followers, stimulates and inspires the followers to achieve outstanding results, as well as helping them grow and build leadership skills by reacting to their specific needs, empowering them with smart objectives and goals, optimistic about the futures, and display continued enthusiasm (Ahmed, 2015).

Table 4. Extent of leadership empowerment as to intellectual stimulation

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My superior includes each of us in addressing organizational problems.	4.09	0.86	Agree
2. My superior stimulates and supports each of us in our every endeavor to solve existing problems using our creativity and innovations.	4.00	0.95	Agree
3. My superior encourages each of us to anticipate possible problem / circumstances that may occur.	4.19	0.83	Agree
4. My superior encourages each of us to handle problems confronting the department.	4.19	0.85	Agree
5. My superior encourages each of us to approach existing problems in innovative ways.	4.10	0.93	Agree
Overall	4.11	0.79	Agree

Table 4 presents the extent of leadership empowerment as to intellectual stimulation. Respondents “agreed” that the concept of “intellectual stimulation” is being practiced in the institution, as evidenced from the obtained overall mean rating of 4.11. Their “superior encourages each of them to handle problems confronting the department” ($x=4.19$, $SD=0.85$) and their “superior encourages each of them to anticipate possible problem/ circumstances that may occur” ($x=4.19$, $SD=0.83$) rank first. This means participants believed that their superior encourages each of them to handle and anticipate problem/circumstances confronting or may occur in the department. These are followed by their “superior encourages each of them to approach existing problems in innovative ways” ($x=4.10$, $SD=0.93$); then by their “superior includes each of them in addressing organizational problems” ($x=4.09$, $SD=0.86$). The least is that their “superior stimulates and supports each of them in their every endeavor to solve existing problems using their creativity and innovations” ($x=4.00$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained SD which is equal to 0.95. In spite of encouraging them to anticipate and handle circumstances in their department, aspiration of the participants to solve the problem with their creativity and innovations is not fully utilized. This could be mean that their superiors follow a certain golden rule.

Innovation is defined as the successful implementation of innovative ideas within an organization as a process (Amabile, 1988). Employees may seek to change some part of their work or their work products during the process in order to obtain a benefit they value (Gilson & May, 2005). Empowered leaders practiced intellectual stimulation (Bass, 1985), and intellectual engagements (Bridger, 2014) by encouraging their followers to identify and solve challenges in a totally and creatively in different ways and autonomy among the members, and by changing the way how they decide; assists to overcome trials by seeing the ‘big picture’ and achieving their goals (Ahmed, 2015).

Table 5. Extent of leadership empowerment as to individualized consideration

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My superior gives individualized mentoring attention to each of us to grow and to develop as a person and as a professional.	3.76	1.07	Agree
2. My superior is hands-on in mentoring each of us in the office.	3.84	1.06	Agree
3. My superior mentors each of us in accordance to our own personal needs.	3.74	1.00	Agree
4. My superior assigns and delegates action learning tasks to each of us in the office.	4.04	0.98	Agree
5. My superior monitors his/her assigned/delegated learning tasks from each of us.	4.00	0.86	Agree
Overall	3.88	0.91	Agree

Table 5 discloses the extent of leadership empowerment as to individualized consideration. Participants “agreed” that the concept of “individualized consideration” is being practiced, as evidenced from the obtained overall mean rating of 3.88. Their “superior assigns and delegates action learning tasks to each of them in the office” ($x=4.04$, $SD=0.98$) ranks first. This means respondents have witnessed that their superior assigns and delegates action learning tasks to each of them in the office. It is followed by their “superior monitors his/her assigned/ delegated learning tasks from each of them” ($x=4.00$, $SD=0.86$); then by their “superior is hands-on in mentoring each of us in the office” ($x=3.84$, $S.D.=1.06$); and the fourth is their “superior gives individualized mentoring attention to each of them to grow and to develop as a person and as a professional” ($x=3.76$, $S.D.=1.07$). The least is their “superior mentors each of them in accordance to their own personal needs” ($x=3.74$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained S.D. which is equal to 1.00.

This could be mean that in spite of assigning, delegating and monitoring the learning tasks, the leader has an efficient full attention in mentoring the participants according to their personal needs. According to Sondreal (2018), employees are more engaged when mentorship is used to discover what inspires and excites them. It allows them to grow by allowing tenured and experienced personnel to share their knowledge and experiences with those who are eager to learn. Mentoring also aids succession planning by preparing competent individuals to take on more leadership roles and preventing knowledge loss during turnover. It also aids in the retention of high-potential employees because they are more valuable.

Table 6. Overall extent of leadership empowerment

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Idealized Influence	3.96	0.78	Agree
Inspirational Motivation	4.04	0.81	Agree
Intellectual Stimulation	4.11	0.79	Agree
Individualized Consideration	3.88	0.91	Agree
Overall	4.00	0.78	Agree

Table 6 reveals the overall extent of leadership empowerment. Based on the table, it has an overall mean rating of 4.00. Superiors practiced first intellectual stimulation ($x=4.11$, $SD=0.79$). Inspirational motivation ($x=4.04$, $SD=0.81$) is closely followed by idealized influence ($x=3.96$, $SD=0.78$). The least practiced is individualized consideration ($x=3.88$, $SD=0.91$). According to Bass (1985), transformed and empowered leader is idealized influence, intellectually stimulated, considerate individually, and motivated inspirationally. Leaders consider individually its followers by recognizing their specific needs, desires and potentials; acts as coach or mentor by giving training sessions; empathizes and encourages the followers to communicate freely in sharing their feelings and ideas so that followers will have ambitions to fulfill self-development and be motivated for the tasks (Ahmed, 2015). Leaders motivate and inspire their followers by stimulating confidence; demonstrating motivation for a commitment to the goals and sense of purpose; communicating the vision comprehensibly, specifically, influential and engaging; showing continued enthusiasm; being optimistic about the futures; and believing in their abilities to emphasize positively (Ahmed, 2015).

Table 7. Readiness towards leadership empowerment as to idealized influence

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am prepared to take my superior as a good role model to me as a leader.	4.13	0.90	Agree
2. I am ready to imitate what my superior has been doing as a leader.	3.90	1.02	Agree
3. I am ready and willing to take risks in my superior's decisions.	3.99	0.91	Agree
4. I am prepared to follow my superior's consistency in all his/her decision making, whether it pleases me or not.	4.15	0.93	Agree
5. I am prepared to exemplify my superior's high level of honesty and integrity in everything he/she does, whether we see it or not.	4.25	0.85	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.08	0.83	Agree

Table 7 shows that the respondents' readiness towards leadership empowerment as to idealized influence has an overall mean rating of 4.08 which means that the respondents "agreed" that they are ready to practice the concept of "idealized influence" as part of leadership empowerment. Participants are "prepared to exemplify their superior's high level of honesty and integrity in everything he/she does, whether they see it or not" ($x=4.25$, $SD=0.85$). This means participants are ready to demonstrate their leaders' high level of honesty and integrity in everything they do at all times. This could mean that they are prepared to witness and see what is really expected to a leader. This is followed by "they prepared to follow their superior's consistency in all his/her decision making, whether it pleases them or not" ($x=4.15$, $SD=0.93$); then, this is followed by they are "prepared to take their superior as a good role model to them as a leader" ($x=4.13$, $SD=0.90$). The fourth is they are "ready and willing to take risks in their superior's decisions" ($x=3.99$, $SD=0.91$) and the least is they are "ready to imitate what their superior has been doing as a leader" ($x=3.90$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained SD which is equal to 1.02.

This implies that respondents are least to be ready to imitate the doings of their leaders. But still having a remark of "agree", this may seem to indicate that participants are not fully prepared to totally imitate what their superior has been doing as a leader. According to Al-Tahitah et al. (2018), leaders may improve their organization's preparation for change by setting common norms and fostering successful teamwork.

Table 8. Extent of leadership empowerment as to inspirational motivation

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am prepared to follow how my superior serves as an inspiration in his/her every action.	4.16	0.87	Agree
2. I am ready to imitate the actions of my superior which give meaning to my work as a follower.	4.15	0.90	Agree
3. I am ready to follow the actions of my superior which challenge me to do better in everything I do.	4.22	0.91	Strongly Agree
4. I am prepared to follow how my superior engages and involves us in the development of our department's vision for the future.	4.24	0.89	Strongly Agree
5. I am prepared to imitate my superior how he/she communicates his/her clear expectations to each of us as part of the team.	4.16	0.89	Agree
Overall	4.19	0.85	Agree

Table 8 reveals that the respondents' readiness towards leadership empowerment as to inspirational motivation has an overall mean rating of 4.19 which implies that the respondents "agreed" that they are prepared to practice the concept of "inspirational motivation" as part of leadership empowerment.

Participants are “prepared to follow how their superior engages and involves them in the development of their department’s vision for the future” ($x=4.24$, $SD=0.89$) ranks first. This implies that respondents are ready to follow how their leaders engage and involve them in organizational planning. This could mean that they are prepared to be a contributor in the development of the institution. This is followed by the indicator, “ready to follow the actions of their superior which challenge them to do better in everything they do” ($x=4.22$, $SD=0.91$). Then, this is followed by the indicator, “prepared to imitate their superior how he/she communicates his/her clear expectations to each of them as part of the team” ($x=4.16$, $SD=0.89$) and they are “prepared to follow how their superior serves as an inspiration in his/her every action” ($x=4.16$, $SD=0.87$). The least is they are “ready to imitate the actions of their superior which give meaning to their work as a follower” ($x=4.15$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained SD which is equal to 0.90. This means participants are least to be ready to imitate the action of their leaders which give meaning to their work. But still having a remark of “agree”, this may seem to indicate that respondents are not fully prepared to totally imitate what their leaders are doing for them to be inspired to their work.

Table 9. Readiness towards leadership empowerment as to intellectual stimulation

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am inspired how my superior includes us in addressing organizational problems.	4.15	0.95	Agree
2. I am prepared to do as how my superior stimulates and supports using our every endeavor to solve existing problems using our creativity and innovations.	4.12	0.94	Agree
3. I am ready to follow how my superior encourages us to anticipate possible problem / circumstances that may occur.	4.15	0.85	Agree
4. I am ready to imitate how my superior encourages each of us to handle problems confronting the department.	4.07	0.89	Agree
5. I am ready to follow how my superior encourages each of us to approach existing problems in innovative ways.	4.25	0.87	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.15	0.84	Agree

Table 9 reveals that the respondents’ readiness towards leadership empowerment as to intellectual stimulation has an overall mean rating of 4.15 which indicates that the respondents “agreed” that they are ready to practice the concept of “intellectual stimulation” as part of leadership empowerment.

Participants are “ready to follow how their superior encourages each of them to approach existing problems in innovative ways” ($x=4.25$, $SD=0.87$). This means participants are ready to follow how their leaders encourage them to approach existing problem in innovative ways. This could mean that they are prepared to trail the ways they are being encouraged by their leaders in giving new methods and tactics in solving a problem. This is followed by the indicator, “ready to follow how their superior encourages them to anticipate possible problem/ circumstances that may occur” ($x=4.15$, $SD=0.85$) and they are “inspired how their superior includes them in addressing organizational problems” ($x=4.15$, $SD=0.95$). The fourth is they are “prepared to do as how their superior stimulates and supports them in their every endeavor to solve existing problems using their creativity and innovations” ($x=4.12$, $SD=0.94$). The least is they are “ready to imitate how their superior encourages each of them to handle problems confronting the department” ($x=4.07$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained SD which is equal to 0.89.

Table 10. Readiness towards leadership empowerment as to individualized consideration

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am prepared as my superior gives individualized mentoring attention to each of us to grow and to develop as a person and as a professional.	4.31	0.85	Strongly Agree
2. I am ready as my superior is hands-on in mentoring each of us.	4.25	0.87	Strongly Agree
3. I am ready to follow my superior in mentoring each of us according to our own personal needs.	4.29	0.90	Strongly Agree
4. I am ready to imitate as my superior assigns and delegates action learning tasks to each of us as his / her followers.	4.25	0.89	Strongly Agree
5. I am ready as my superior monitors his/her assigned/delegated learning tasks from each of us.	4.29	0.85	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.28	0.84	Strongly Agree

Table 10 exposes that the respondents’ readiness towards leadership empowerment as to individualized consideration has an overall mean rating of 4.28 which means that the respondents “strongly agreed” that they are prepared to practice the concept of “individualized consideration” as part of leadership empowerment. Participants are “prepared as their superior gives individualized mentoring attention to each of them to grow and to develop as a person and as a professional” ($x=4.31$, $SD=0.85$) ranks first. This implies respondents are ready as their leaders give them individualized mentoring attention to grow and to develop as a personal and as a professional. This could be mean that participants are prepared to embrace the different ways how to improve themselves holistically. This is followed by they are “ready as their superior monitors his/her assigned/delegated learning tasks from each of them” ($x=4.29$, $SD=0.85$) and they are “ready to follow their superior in mentoring each of them according to their own personal needs” ($x=4.29$, $SD=0.90$).

This is followed by they are “ready as their superior is hands-on in mentoring each of them” ($x=4.25$, $SD=0.87$) and they are “ready to imitate as their superior assigns and delegates action learning tasks to each of them as his/her followers” ($x=4.25$) with a very dispersed data and this inference was based from the obtained SD which is equal to 0.89 as the least. This means participants are least to be ready to imitate the way their leaders assign and delegate learning tasks to them and be hands- on in mentoring them. But still having a remark of “strongly agree”, this may seem to indicate that respondents are not fully prepared to totally be assigned and delegated to a task and be over directed. This may be due to unidentified things to be considered.

According to the result of the study of Ogola et al. (2017), when a leader practices individualized consideration, he or she considers the uniqueness of each staff. Leaders connect each follower’s priorities to the organization’s growth. It is found that employees were able to do their duties effectively because the chief executive officer (CEO) supervised and instructed them on how to accomplish their roles and always recognized their contributions; thus, employees put extra effort in their work.

Table 11. Overall readiness towards leadership empowerment

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Idealized Influence	4.08	0.83	Agree
Inspirational Motivation	4.19	0.85	Agree
Intellectual Stimulation	4.15	0.84	Agree
Individualized Consideration	4.28	0.84	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.17	0.79	Agree

Table 11 reveals that the respondents’ readiness towards leadership empowerment the overall mean rating is 4.17. Individualized consideration ($x=4.28$, $SD=0.84$) ranks first; followed by inspirational motivation ($x=4.19$, $SD=0.85$). Intellectual stimulation ($x=4.15$, $SD=0.84$) ranks third and least is idealized influence ($x=4.08$, $SD=0.83$). Based on the interpretation, respondents agreed that they are ready and prepared for the full implementation of empowered leadership using the transformational leadership theory. According to Ogola et al. (2017), high performance is attained when a leader appreciates employees’ achievements, instills confidence, encourages self-development, and provides good communication, mentoring, and coaching.

Table 12. Correlation between leadership empowerment and readiness

Variable	Pearson r	p value	QI	Decision
Extent of leadership empowerment practiced and the participant’s readiness towards leadership	0.76	0.09	High Correlation	NS

Legend: NS = not significant; S = significant at .05

Table 12 provides the correlation between leadership empowerment and readiness. The extent of leadership empowerment practiced and the participant’s readiness towards leadership empowerment is highly correlated, and this was based on the obtained Pearson r which is 0.76. This can be obtained that these variables are not statistically significant.

According to Al-Tahitah et. al (2018), some studies have examined the relationship between transformational leadership and readiness for change. In this respect, Allen (2007)’s study showed that transformational leadership has a positive impact on the perceptions of an organization’s readiness for change. Another study by Santhidran et al. (2013), which hypothesized that leadership is positively related to change readiness and discovered a significant positive relationship between leadership and change readiness.

On the empirical study of Allen et al. (2013), the researchers assumed that transformational leadership has a significant relationship with organizational change readiness. Similarly, a recent study by Saragih (2015) claimed that individual readiness for organizational change could be a huge obstacle to implementing a successful organizational change. The researcher emphasized that transformational leadership plays a strategic and crucial role in accomplishing organizational change.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The extent of leadership empowerment practiced as to four concepts namely idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration were revealed in the study. The participants agreed that these concepts are being practiced in the institution. Particularly that their superior exemplifies a high level of honesty and integrity in everything he/she does, whether they see it or not and that their superior is willing to take risks in his/her decision making. This is shown as most of the respondents concurred that their superior engages and involves them in the development of their department’s vision for the future. According to them, their superior encourages each of them to handle problems confronting the department and that their superior encourages each of them to anticipate possible problem / circumstances that may occur. Most of them concurred that their superior assigns and delegates action learning tasks to each of them in the office.

As to readiness, participants are prepared to exemplify their superior’s high level of honesty and integrity in everything he or she does, whether they see it or not. They are prepared to follow how their superior engages and involves them in the development of their department’s vision for the future. It is also noted that the non-academic personnel are ready to follow how their superior encourages each of them to approach existing problems in innovative ways. Participants are prepared as their superior gives individualized mentoring attention to each of them to grow and to develop as a person and as a professional.

It is also revealed that there is no significant relationship between extent of leadership practiced and the participants' readiness towards leadership empowerment. However, the extent of leadership practiced and the participants' readiness towards leadership correlates and this explains that individual consideration contributes to the very high correlation due to their superior giving them individualized mentoring attention to each of us to grow and to develop as a person and as a professional.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the output of this study, Leadership Enhancement Program, must be implemented to help the academic institution empower the non-academic personnel for more productivity. Leaders must always to always communicate and listen to employee concerns and spend time mentoring and coaching them. Recently offered programs must continue like the Scholarship/Educational Grant, not only for Academic employees but more specifically for Non-Academic employees or the administrative staffs to help them grow as a person and as a professional. A follow-up research may be conducted in exploring variables other than those investigated in the present study that may improve leadership program of the institution such as viewpoints of the middle and top managers may be included and the association of perceived organizational support for innovation and organizational trust may be considered. The result of the study may be duplicated to other departments of the institution to encourage employees to excel in their workplace.

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